

INTENSITY OF HEALTH PROBLEMS AND HEALTH HAZARDS OF THE WORKERS IN THE UNORGANIZED SECTOR-A THEORETICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract:

The study of the informal sector has been a key focus area in Development Economics literature. Particularly since the 1970s, it has drawn extensive attention of researchers and policy makers. The considerable overlaps between informal sector employment and poverty are testimony to the phenomenon of the “working poor.” In the present context of globalization, there has been a renewed interest in issues relating to the informal sector such as their employment, health problems etc.

The unorganized sector/ informal sector has a crucial role in our economy in terms of employment generation and its contribution to the national domestic product, savings and capital formation. This sector generates income earning opportunities for a large number of people by employment generation and leads to poverty alleviation. Predominance of informal employment has been one of the central features of the labour market scenario in India. As per the estimates of 66th round NSS survey (2009-10), the unorganized workers constitutes 93 percent of the total workforce in the Indian economy.

According to the National Commission for Enterprises in the Unorganized Sector (NCEUS) Report 2007, 79 percent of the informal or unorganized workers in India belong to poor and vulnerable group. The Report indicates that they live and work in unhygienic conditions and are susceptible to many infections and chronic diseases. The persistent poverty and disease syndromes have pushed their families to a state of de-capitalization and indebtedness to meet their day to day contingencies. Both macro and micro level studies on the use of health care services show that these workers are forced to spend a higher proportion of their income on health care. The high incidence of morbidity cuts their household budget in both ways, ie, not only do they have to spend a large amount of money and resources on medical care, but are also unable to earn during the period of illness. Very often, they have to borrow funds at very high interest rate to meet both medical expenditure and other household consumption needs. One possible consequence of this could be to push these families into a zone of permanent poverty.

Introduction

Recently, “Economics of Health” is being acknowledged as an important branch of Development Economics. Hence, it is given high priority by planners, thinkers and economists not only in India but also all over the world. Attainment of good health is a significant component of human capital and the health status of the citizens reflect the economic development of a nation. Assuring a minimum level of health care to the population is a critical constituent of the development process. The maxim that ‘health is wealth’ highlights the increasing importance of good health as an integral part of social development. As it is an important indicator of development, health is increasingly being seen as a matter of concern for development rather than just a medical one. Health is influenced by different indicators like employment, income, educational attainment, social groups, level of medical awareness, accessibility to health care and availability of health services. Improvement in the health status of population not only contributes directly to human happiness, but also enhances capabilities and freedom. The

development of a society, rich or poor, can be judged by the quality of its population's health, how fairly health is distributed across the social spectrum and the degree of protection provided against disadvantages due to ill-health.

While the interrelationship between good health, well being and good standard of living are acknowledged, the strong link between poverty and ill health had to be considered. According to Planning Commission, 39 million Indians were pushed to poverty because of ill health every year. For people living below the poverty line, an illness definitely represents a threat to their income earning capacity ultimately leading the family falling into a debt trap. The onset of a long and expensive illness can drive even the rich into poverty. High health care costs and related expenditure can lead to the exacerbation of poverty. Besides, poor health leads to deficiency of human capabilities and it also shows the level of deprivation among the people. As argued by Amartya Sen, "poverty must be seen as the deprivation of basic capabilities rather than merely low level of income." Poor health condition can be a major source of capability deprivation and hence, a cause for unemployment and poverty. As such, poor health is considered as the major constraint of development. At this juncture, it is appropriate to highlight the intensity of ill health and associated health problems of the workers of unorganised sector, mainly belonging to the lower strata of the society, but contributing a major share of country's GDP.

Objectives of the study

The specific objectives of the study are given below.

1. To identify the perceived health problems of the workers.
2. To assess the health infrastructure and medical facilities utilised by the workers for health care.

Methodology and analytical frame work of the research work

The study is empirical and analytical in nature based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data is collected from a diversified sample of 700 workers belonging to the unorganized sector. Secondary data is collected from different sources such as WHO and ILO reports, Indian Census figures, estimates of NSSO, Directorate of Economics and Statistics, NCEUS, periodicals, journals, newspapers and various micro and macro level studies related to the topic.

With regard to the selection of universe, we selected two districts of Kerala, (Ernakulam and Idukki) for elaborate field investigation. For considering the universe of urban area, the researcher selected two municipalities from Ernakulam districts (Kothamangalam and Muvattupuzha) and one (Thodupuzha) from Idukki district for field survey. The universe of rural area constitutes four panchayats of Ernakulam district such as Nellikuzhy, Pindimana, Keerampara and Kuttampuzha and one panchayat from Idukki district, Vannapuram. Stratified sampling technique is applied for the selection of workers

To analyze the data collected from field survey, we had applied various analytical tools like averages, percentages, graphical method etc. and presented them in pie diagrams, bar diagrams, charts, tables, Chi- square test etc. Analysis of the data relating to health hazards and medical treatment correspond to the reference period of one year.

For a clear perspective of the data analysis, this article is divided into two sections- section A and section B. The documentation of the incidence of various health hazards, their frequency of occurrence and the allied issues among

the workers are presented in section A. Section B illustrates the provision of medical facilities in the study area and its utilization by the workers focusing upon the extent to which they are availed and benefits received by them.

Section A: Incidence and intensity of health hazards of the workers

In this section, the researcher undertakes a detailed enquiry into the health hazards of the workers with respect to the area (rural- urban), gender (male-female) and type of economic activity (agriculture, manufacturing and construction and service). In this context, the nature of diseases, frequency of their occurrence, incidence of smoking and alcoholism among the workers are examined.

Illness profile of the workers

Total number of illness episode reported in the study area among 700 workers during the last year was 1667 comprising of 842 (50.51%) from rural area and 825 (49.49%) from urban area. Out of this, 117 (7.02%) illness constitute chronic diseases like heart diseases, liver diseases, bone fracture, etc, 657 (39.41%) are seasonal diseases like fever, asthma, etc and 893 (53.57%) are general diseases like head ache, body pain/ back pain, etc. An important aspect noticed is that most of these diseases are closely related to the nature of their job. Long hours of continuous work under poor and unhygienic conditions cause many diseases. Gender wise distribution of diseases shows that female workers (51.35%) had more health problems than males (48.65%) (Table 1). On the basis of nature of diseases, chronic diseases are reported more among female workers whereas seasonal diseases are higher among male workers (40.32%). But general diseases are almost same for both males and females.

Area wise analysis of illness episode indicates that there is not much difference but slightly higher among the workers of rural area. Seasonal diseases are reported more from rural workers while general diseases are higher among urban workers.

Table 1 Area and gender wise distribution of illness episode of workers on the basis of nature of diseases (in numbers)

Nature of diseases	Rural	Urban	Male	Female	Total
General	439 (52.14)	454 (55.03)	434 (53.51)	459 (53.62)	893 (53.57)
Seasonal	344 (40.86)	313 (37.94)	327 (40.32)	330 (38.55)	657 (39.41)
Chronic	59 (7.00)	58 (7.03)	50 (6.17)	67 (7.83)	117 (7.02)
Total	842 (50.51) (100)	825 (49.49) (100)	811(48.65) (100)	856 (51.35) (100)	1667 (100) (100)

Source: Primary data. Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to total.

Sector wise distribution of illness episode stated in table 2 shows that out of 537 illness episode reported from agricultural sector during the last year, 312 (58.10%) are general diseases, 183 (34.08%) are seasonal diseases and 42 (7.82%) are chronic diseases. In the manufacturing and construction sector, a total of 610 cases are reported during the last year out of which, 349 (57.22%), 207 (33.93%) and 54 (8.85%) are general, seasonal and chronic diseases respectively. In the service sector, out of the total 520 illness episode, the case of chronic diseases are less (4.04%) while seasonal diseases are higher (51.35%). Considering all the sectors, seasonal diseases are higher among service sector workers (51.35%) whereas general diseases are higher among the agricultural and manufacturing sector workers.

Table 2 Sector wise distribution of illness episode (in numbers)

Nature of diseases	Agriculture	Manufacturing and construction	Service	Total
General	312 (58.10)	349 (57.22)	232 (44.61)	893 (53.57)
Seasonal	183 (34.08)	207 (33.93)	267 (51.35)	657 (39.41)
Chronic	42 (7.82)	54 (8.85)	21 (4.04)	117 (7.02)
Total	537 (32.21) (100)	610 (36.59) (100)	520 (31.19) (100)	1667 (100) (100)

Source: Primary data. Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to total.

Job related health hazards

Majority of the workers, mainly females reported that they have various health problems related to their work. Long hours of continuous work, poor and unhygienic working conditions, frequent overtime work, lack of adequate work intervals, extreme heat, cold, rain, etc cause numerous health hazards among the workers. Out of the total sample of 700 workers, 507 (72.43%) reported to have health problems due to nature of work.

Comparative analysis of male and female workers about job related health hazards by using chi-square test indicates that there is significant difference between them in this regard because P value (.013) is lower than the significant level of .05. Job related health hazards are higher among the female workers (76.10%) than male workers (68.45%).

Table 3 :Gender wise distribution of workers on the basis of job related health problems (in numbers)

Job related health problems	Male	Female	Total	Chi-square	P value
Yes	230 (68.45)	277 (76.10)	507 (72.43)	6.117	.013
No	106 (31.55)	87 (23.90)	193 (27.57)		
Total	336 (100)	364 (100)	700 (100)		

Source: Primary data. Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to total.

Sector wise analysis of workers about job related health hazards by using chi-square test indicates that there is significant difference between them in this regard because P value (.001) is lower. Job related health hazards are relatively higher among the workers of manufacturing and construction sector (78.75%) and lower among the workers of service sector (63.40%). Comparatively better working conditions, less work effort and better facilities attributed to the low health hazards of service sector workers.

Table 4 Sector wise distribution of workers on the basis of job related health problems (in numbers)

Job related health problems	Agriculture	Manufacturing and construction sector	Service sector	Total	Chi-square	P value
Yes	169 (75.11)	189 (78.75)	149 (63.40)	507 (72.43)	15.184	.001
No	56 (24.89)	51 (21.25)	86 (36.60)	193 (27.57)		
Total	225 (100)	240 (100)	235 (100)	700 (100)		

Source: computed by researcher on the basis of survey data. Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to total.

Frequency of health problems

To study about the intensity of health problems of the workers, the frequency of their occurrence at different intervals is examined which could highlight the severity of health hazards and the consequent financial burden.

It is seen that 31.59 percent of females and 26.79 percent of males are affected by various health problems regularly and continuously and this is incurred among 32.57 percent of the workers in the urban area and 26 percent in the rural area. On the other hand, 20.57 percent of the workers in the urban area had health problems rarely or

occasionally whereas it is 27.14 percent in the rural area. The analysis indicates that frequency and intensity of health hazards are higher among the urban workers and also more among females.

Table 5 Area and gender wise distribution of workers on the basis of frequency of health problems (in numbers)

Frequency of health problems	Rural	Urban	Male	Female	Total
Regularly	91 (26.00)	114 (32.57)	90 (26.79)	115 (31.59)	205 (29.29)
Weekly	76 (21.71)	76 (21.71)	76 (22.61)	76 (20.88)	152 (21.71)
Monthly	88 (25.14)	88 (25.14)	77 (22.91)	99 (27.20)	176 (25.14)
Rarely	95 (27.14)	72 (20.57)	93 (27.68)	74 (20.33)	167 (23.86)
Total	350 (100)	350 (100)	336 (100)	364 (100)	700 (100)

Source: Primary data. Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to total.

Sector wise analysis indicates that 26.67 percent of workers of agricultural sector, 32.08 percent of manufacturing and construction sector and 28.94 percent of service sector workers had regular and continuous health problems. So the intensity of the problem is severe in manufacturing and construction sector. They work without considering their ill-health as their earnings form the main source of their livelihood which had seriously affected their working capacities.

Table 6 : Sector wise distribution of workers on the basis of frequency of health problems (in numbers)

Frequency of health problems	Agriculture	Manufacturing and construction	Service	Total
Regularly	60 (26.67)	77 (32.08)	68 (28.94)	205 (29.29)
Weekly	53 (23.56)	54 (22.50)	45 (19.14)	152 (21.71)
Monthly	58 (25.77)	62 (25.83)	56 (23.83)	176 (25.14)
Rarely	54 (24.00)	47 (19.58)	66 (28.09)	167 (23.86)
Total	225 (100)	240 (100)	235 (100)	700 (100)

Source: Primary data. Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to total.

Section B: Provision of medical facilities and its utilization

In this section, the researcher briefly discusses the availability and utilization of medical facilities by the workers in the study area.

Availability of medical facilities in the study area

Access to hospitals in terms of distance is considered as one of the major factors in determining the utilization of the health care system. The study shows that 30 percent of the workers had this facility within 5 km whereas 50 percent had to travel 10 to 15 km and 20 percent had to travel more than 20 km. In fact, the travel expenditure form a main component of the health expenditure. People in rural and backward areas had lesser access to proper health care facilities and the existing facilities are much less than the requirements.

The people of the study area mainly depend upon three major systems of medicines- Allopathy, Ayurveda and homeopathy. Among them, allopathy accounts for the highest share with 81 percent, Homeopathy accounts for 12 percent and only 7 percent depend upon Ayurveda for curing their ailments.

Selection of hospital

During the field survey, detailed investigation is conducted among the workers regarding the type of hospital, ie whether private or Government for which they seek medical aid.

It is found that majority of the workers (61.14%) depend on private medical facilities who mainly belong to better socio-economic status and those depending government hospitals are from lower socio-economic status.

The table 7 indicates that 62.20 percent of the males and 60.16 percent of the females depend on private medical facilities for their treatment. The urban workers had a higher preference for private hospitals (62.57%) than rural workers (59.71%) for medical treatment.

Table 7 Area and gender wise distribution of workers on the basis of selection of hospital (in numbers)

Selection of hospital	Rural	Urban	Male	Female	Total
Private	209 (59.71)	219 (62.57)	209 (62.20)	219 (60.16)	428 (61.14)
Government	141 (40.29)	131 (37.43)	127 (37.80)	145 (39.84)	272 (38.86)
Total	350 (100)	350 (100)	336 (100)	364 (100)	700 (100)

Source: Primary data. Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to total.

With regard to the reasons for opting private hospitals for getting treatment, it is seen that even though the cost of treatment is very high, they provide better treatment, proper diagnosis and better facilities. The respondents state that better personal consideration and fair treatment are provided by the staff of private hospitals.

On the other hand, nearly 40 percent of the workers expressed their dissatisfaction with the functioning of government hospitals. While 20 percent pointed out the non availability of doctors, about 32 percent states that medicines are not available in stock and bribing was rampant. The main drawbacks are lack of availability of adequate drugs, poor investigation facilities, unsuitable timings and callous behaviours of the health personnel. Many of the workers reported that the inconvenient timings of the primary health centres make it impossible to get treatment as the working time of PHC coincides with their working hours.

Decision to postpone medical treatment

Private expenditure form the major portion of health expenditure of the sample workers and out of this, out of pocket expenditure form a significant share. As majority of the workers depend on private hospitals which impose high financial burden upon the workers, some of them frequently postpone medical treatment at the time of illness.

Out of the 700 workers, 32.29 percent have postponed medical treatment several times due to various reasons. This constitutes 33.79 percent of females and 30.65 percent of males. Comparative study between them about the postponement of medical treatment at the time of illness by chi-square test shows that there is no significant difference between them in this regard because P value (.371) is higher than .05.

Table 8 Gender wise distribution of workers on the basis of postponement of treatment (in numbers)

Postponement of medical treatment	Male	Female	Total	Chi-square	P value
Yes	103 (30.65)	123 (33.79)	226 (32.29)	.802	.371
No	233 (69.35)	241 (66.21)	474 (67.71)		
Total	336 (100)	364 (100)	700 (100)		

Source: Primary data. Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to total.

Considering the three sectors, the proportion of postponement is higher in the manufacturing and construction sector (34.17%) and least in the service sector (29.79%).

Figure 1 Sector wise distribution of workers on the basis of postponement of treatment

Source: Primary data.

Area wise analysis revealed that 32.86 percent of workers in rural area and 31.71 percent in urban area had postponed medical treatment at the time of illness. The comparative study among them in this aspect by chi-square test shows that there is no significant difference between them in this regard because P value (.809) is higher than .05.

Table 9 Area wise distribution of workers on the basis of postponement of treatment (in numbers)

Postponement of medical treatment	Rural	Urban	Total	Chi square	P value
Yes	115 (32.86)	111 (31.71)	226 (32.29)	.058	.809
No	235 (67.14)	239 (68.29)	474 (67.71)		
Total	350 (100)	350 (100)	700 (100)		

Source: Primary data. Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to total

Reasons for postponement of medical treatment

Various factors are responsible for the postponement of medical treatment at the time of illness. The reasons stated are constraints relating to money (42.04%) and time (48.67%). In the rural area, we can see that out of 115 workers who had postponed treatment at the time of illness, 43.48 percent had done it due to lack of money, 42.61 percent due to lack of time and 13.91 percent due to lack of medical facilities. In urban area, the corresponding figures are 40.54 percent, 54.95 percent and 4.50 percent respectively. It denotes that money constraint is comparatively higher in the rural area while time constraint is prominent in urban area. Likewise, money constraint is a serious problem for females while time constraint is for males.

Table 10 Area and gender wise distribution of workers on the basis of reasons for postponement of treatment (in numbers)

Reasons for postponement	Rural	Urban	Male	Female	Total
Lack of money	50 (43.48)	45 (40.54)	36 (34.95)	59 (47.97)	95 (42.04)
Lack of time	49 (42.61)	61 (54.95)	57 (55.34)	53 (43.09)	110 (48.67)
Lack of medical facilities	16 (13.91)	5 (4.50)	10 (9.71)	11 (8.94)	21 (9.29)
Total	115 (100)	111 (100)	103 (100)	123 (100)	226 (100)

Source: Primary data. Figures in parentheses indicate percentages to total.

Considering the three sectors, 43.24 percent of workers from agriculture sector, 45.12 percent from manufacturing and construction sector and 37.14 percent from service sector postponed medical treatment due to lack of money. Hence money constraint is not a serious problem in the service sector but time constraint (57.14%) is significant.

Figure 2 Sector wise distribution of workers on the basis of reasons for postponement of treatment

Source: Primary data.

Conclusion

A number of important findings have emerged from this analysis. It is highlighted from the study that most of the health problems reported by the workers are closely related to their job. Almost three-fourth of the workers had health problems and they are intense among the females and in the manufacturing and construction sector and lesser in service sector. With regard to the frequency of health problems, females face them regularly and it is higher among the agricultural and construction sector workers. Eventhough the cost of treatment in private hospital is very high compared to government hospital, majority of the workers prefer to have medical treatment from private hospital. As the cost of illness and medical treatment impose high burden upon the workers, there are many cases of postponing medical treatment.

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